

Method and schematic diagram for converting quality into energy

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Abstract: This article presents a method for converting the mass of materials into energy, which can be achieved with existing scientific and experimental conditions. Its efficiency and safety are far greater than controllable nuclear fusion, while the development cost is much lower than controllable nuclear fusion. Once realized, humanity will have endless energy and interstellar travel will be just around the corner.

Theoretical basis: Article in the high-energy particle physics section of the vixra website: Exploration and schematic diagram of microscopic particle models, ID: vixra: 2312-0032, the article describes the causes of the Big Bang, the principles of material formation, the composition of protons and neutrons, the principles of beta and anti beta decay, the formation and evolution of various elementary particles, and based on this, deduces the principles and methods of converting material mass into energy.

Principle: The core of a neutron is composed of two down quarks and one up quark, which is actually composed of three down quarks and one positron. The π^+ meson is composed of three anti down quarks, and its structure and vibration frequency are similar to that of a neutron. Therefore, the π^+ meson can penetrate the outer shell of the neutron and react with the neutron core.

Method: Using the formula: $Z=n+\pi^+$

The explanation is as follows: When a π^+ meson collides with a neutron, within an appropriate energy range, the π^+ meson can penetrate the neutron shell, react with the three negative particles inside the neutron, undergo annihilation, and the photons in the neutron shell lose the attraction of the core and are completely released. The mass of both the neutron and the π^+ meson is converted into energy.

The following legend shows the reaction principles and results of protons and antiprotons, neutrons and antineutrons, π^- mesons and protons, and π^+ mesons and neutrons.

Protons and antiprotons have the same mass, the same vibration frequency, and the same internal structure, but opposite charges. When they come into contact, the Coulomb force of attraction causes them to combine. The three down quarks in the proton's nucleus and the three anti-down quarks in the antiproton's nucleus combine and revert to photons. The photon streams around the periphery of the proton and antiproton lose the attraction of the nucleus and burst out in the form of gamma rays. The two positrons in the proton's nucleus and the two electrons in the antiproton's nucleus simultaneously combine and annihilate, and all their mass is converted into energy.

Note: When a down quark combines with a positron, it shows a charge of $+2/3$, which is an up quark. When an anti-down quark combines with an electron, it shows a charge of $-2/3$, which is an anti-up quark.

Neutrons and antineutrons, with the same mass, the same vibration frequency, and the same internal structure, but opposite charges, when they come into contact, the Coulomb attraction brings them together. The three down quarks in the neutron's core and the three anti-down quarks in the antineutron's core combine, reverting to photons. The photon streams on the periphery of the neutron and antineutron, losing the attraction of the core, burst out in the form of gamma rays. The positrons in the neutron's core and the electrons in the antineutron's core simultaneously combine and annihilate, converting all their mass into energy.

The π^- meson is composed of three negative sub-particles. Its core is similar to that of a proton. Under the attraction of Coulomb force, the π^- meson can penetrate the proton's shell and react with a positive sub-particle in the proton's core, resulting in their mutual annihilation and the proton decaying into a neutron. The three negative sub-particles in the neutron's core have a greater influence range than the positive sub-particle, so the π^- meson cannot penetrate the neutron's shell and no reaction can occur.

Although neutrons show a neutral overall charge, the influence range of the three negative sub-particles in the core is greater than that of the positive electron. When a π^+ meson collides with a neutron, it can penetrate the neutron's outer shell and react with the three negative sub-particles in the neutron's core, combining to form a photon. The photon flow around the neutron loses the attraction of the core and bursts, with all their mass being converted into energy.

Conclusion: As can be seen from the legend above, proton and antiproton, neutron and antineutron, that is, matter and antimatter collide and annihilate, converting all their mass into energy. However, with existing technology, manufacturing antimatter is difficult and costly, and cannot be applied on a large scale.

The π^- - meson collides with a proton and reacts with a positron inside the proton to annihilate it, causing the proton to undergo anti beta decay and become a neutron.

π^+ mesons collide with neutrons, undergo annihilation, and all their mass is converted into energy. π^+ mesons and neutrons are relatively easy to manufacture, and as long as suitable methods are found, they can be produced and applied on a large scale.

Conclusion: With existing scientific technology and experimental equipment, the above methods can be studied and experimented with without the need for high temperature and high pressure, and without generating large-scale energy explosions, thus ensuring excellent safety. The primitive energy of the Big Bang is hidden in every atom, opening up the primitive energy of matter and realizing the conversion of material quality and energy is a big step for humanity to enter higher civilization, which deserves high attention and active attempts. I will publish this theory and method to the public and hope that scientists and research institutions around the world who are interested will participate in the demonstration and experimentation, and work together for the progress of human civilization.

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